

ALCULATION OF EXPENSES AND INCOME IN THE PROCESS OF NATURAL GAS DELIVERY

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Abstract. This study analyzes the expenses and income involved in the process of delivering natural gas to consumers. Using the example of capital expenditure calculations, the economic efficiency of installing new pipelines, replacing outdated ones, project planning, and other necessary technical measures is examined. The total costs for each type of activity are identified, and the overall project cost is analyzed.

Keywords: Natural gas, capital expenditure, economic analysis, pipeline installation, income, depreciation, investment.

Introduction. Efficient use of energy resources and their delivery to the population is one of the key directions in the development of the modern economy. In particular, the process of delivering natural gas to consumers requires a substantial amount of financial and technical resources. It is important to determine capital expenditures, conduct an economic analysis, and evaluate the efficiency of this process.

This article analyzes the financial indicators of works carried out in the natural gas delivery process—such as installing new pipelines, replacing outdated ones, and other technical measures. Based on this analysis, the economic feasibility of the projects is determined, and optimal investment directions are proposed.

Analyzing the expenses and income in the natural gas delivery process and calculating financial indicators is essential.

Table

1

Calculation of Capital Expenditures for Natural Gas Delivery to Consumers

Type of Expense	Duration	Quantity	Unit Cost (USD)	Total Cost (USD)
Installation of new pipelines	1 year	10 km	50,000	500,000
Replacement of outdated pipelines	1 year	4 km	50,000	200,000
Design and construction	1 year	1 project	150,000	150,000
Installation of compressor	1 year	2 units	50,000	100,000

Type of Expense	Duration	Quantity	Unit Cost (USD)	Total Cost (USD)
stations				
Installation of monitoring and control system	1 year	1 project	50,000	50,000
New equipment	1 year	10 units	5,000	50,000
Training and staff development	1 year	10 persons	5,000	50,000
Total				1,075,000

The following indicators are taken into account to implement the project. Capital expenditures are allocated for the construction of new infrastructure and the replacement of outdated pipelines.

1.Installation of New Pipelines:

Includes the cost of pipelines and installation works required for laying new pipelines. The cost of installing 10 km of pipelines is calculated at USD 50,000 per kilometer.

2.Replacement of Outdated Pipelines:

Includes the cost of replacing outdated pipelines and the associated installation works. The cost of replacing 4 km of pipelines is calculated at USD 50,000 per kilometer.

3.Design and Construction:

Covers the overall design and construction works of the project.

4.Installation of Compressor Stations:

Includes the cost of installing 2 compressor stations, each at a price of USD 50,000, to maintain and transmit gas pressure.

5.Installation of Monitoring and Control System:

Covers the cost of installing a system for monitoring and controlling gas delivery.

6.New Equipment:

Involves the purchase of 10 new devices for measurement and monitoring, each costing USD 5,000.

7.Training and Staff Development:

Includes the cost of training workers in new technologies and systems. Capital expenditures are primarily allocated for the construction of new infrastructure and the renewal of outdated pipelines.

Table 2
Calculation of Capital Expenditures

Type of Expense	Cost (USD)
Installation of new pipelines	500,000
Replacement of outdated pipelines	200,000
Design and construction	150,000
Technical equipment	100,000
Total	950,000

Operational expenditures include maintenance, repair, and general operational costs.

Table 3
Calculation of Operational Expenditures in Natural Gas Delivery

Type of Expense	Cost (USD)
Technical maintenance	50,000
Repair costs	30,000
Labor force	100,000
Administrative expenses	20,000
Total	210,000

Revenue from Natural Gas Sales and Fees for Additional Services

Revenue. This includes proceeds from the sale of gas and payments received for additional services.

Table 4
Revenue from Natural Gas Sales

Source	Revenue (USD/year)
Gas sales	1,200,000
Additional services	50,000

Source	Revenue (USD/year)
Total	1,250,000

Financial Indicators

Financial indicators are used to determine the economic efficiency of a project or process.

Annual Profit:

Revenue – Operational Expenses

1,250,000 USD – 210,000 USD = **1,040,000 USD**

Return on Investment (ROI):

(Annual Profit / Capital Expenditures) × 100

(1,040,000 USD / 950,000 USD) × 100 = **109.47%**

Operating Margin:

(Annual Profit / Revenue) × 100

(1,040,000 USD / 1,250,000 USD) × 100 = **83.2%**

Development of Natural Gas Supply to Consumers in Uzbekistan: Challenges and Proposals for Improvement. As a result of studying the development of the natural gas supply sector in Uzbekistan, including its current issues and areas for improvement, the following conclusions and recommendations have been formulated.

Uzbekistan ranks among the top ten countries in the world in terms of natural gas production and export volumes. A large portion of natural gas produced in Uzbekistan is exported; another significant portion is used as raw material and fuel in various sectors of the national economy, while the remainder is consumed by the population. Natural gas contributes over 10% to the total value of exported goods and services.

Currently, 83.2% of the population in Uzbekistan has access to natural gas, including 75.5% of the rural population. This is not only one of the highest rates in Central Asia but also globally. In many developed countries, household consumption of natural gas does not exceed 20%. Despite such a high rate of gas coverage, there are still numerous rural areas in several regions that remain unconnected. Ensuring gas supply to these rural settlements remains one of the most urgent tasks today, especially considering that many of these areas lack alternative fuel sources like wood or coal.

Among the challenges in the gas supply sector, the installation of household gas meters and establishing full control over gas consumption are of critical importance. Due to inefficiencies and uncontrolled losses, the gas input-output

balance does not match. The difference between the volume of gas obtained and the volume consumed indicates significant losses. Such unaccounted “losses” can be minimized by timely data collection from gas meters and by improving accounting systems and enhancing consumer control.

Stable natural gas supply to the population—especially during winter months when shortages occur—can be ensured by addressing issues such as upgrading old pipelines, adjusting their diameter and pressure capacity as necessary, and renewing the infrastructure.

Another important issue is the widespread use of non-standard gas appliances and burners by consumers, which leads to excessive gas wastage and causes many accidents. Solving this issue is also vital for the gas supply sector.

Illegal connections to the gas networks and unauthorized usage, as well as the inability to regularly and fully collect monthly meter readings in residential areas, remain among the most pressing issues. To solve these problems, it is necessary to:

- promote efficient use of natural gas (reduce unnecessary losses),
- standardize household gas appliances,
- enhance control over gas consumption,
- install unique numbered seals on consumer gas meters,
- support financially unstable strategic enterprises (whose gas supply must not be interrupted) through state-sponsored financial rehabilitation to improve their solvency.

A detailed list of expenditures for laying new gas pipelines and replacing outdated pipelines that do not meet modern standards has been compiled, and the volume of associated costs has been calculated.

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